

SIGNIFICANCE OF PSYCHOLINGUISTIC RESEARCH

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Abstract: This article talks about the conditions for the emergence of psycholinguistics. That is, the direction of linguistic psychology, its uniqueness and necessity today. His role in the process of perception and understanding of text has not yet been sufficiently studied, which, in turn, requires serious attention to the issue of determining the rules for text analysis and semantic perception.

Key words: psycholinguistics, linguistic psychology, speech, speech pathology, language, speech genesis, text, recipient.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПСИХОЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ.

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Аннотация: В данной статье говорится об условиях возникновения психолингвистики. То есть направление лингвистической психологии, ее уникальность и необходимость сегодня. Его роль в процессе восприятия и понимания текста еще недостаточно изучена, что, в свою очередь, требует серьезного внимания к вопросу определения правил анализа текста и смыслового восприятия.

Ключевые слова: психолингвистика, лингвистическая психология, речь, речевая патология, язык, речевогенез, текст, реципиент.

PSIXOLINGVISTIK TADQIQOTLARNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada psixolingvistikaning paydo bo‘lish shartlari haqida so‘z boradi. Ya’ni, lingvistik psixologiyaning yo‘nalishi, uning o‘ziga xosligi va bugungi kundagi zaruriyati. Uning matni idrok etish va tushunish jarayonida tutgan o‘rni hali yetarlicha o‘rganilmagan, bu esa, o‘z navbatida, matn tahlili va

semantik idrok etish qoidalarini aniqlash masalasiga jiddiy e'tibor qaratishni talab etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: psixolingvistika, lingvistik psixologiya, nutq, defektologiya, til, matn, qabul qiluvchi.

INTRODUCTION

Language is an object of investigation both in linguistics and in psychology, due to the fact that it appears in speech activity. Based on this, as a synthesis of these two sciences, the direction of psycholinguistics (linguopsychology) was created at the intersection. He studies the process of internal speech verification, speech reception, and language acquisition. This term was first used by the American psychologist N. Pronko in 1946, and has been widely used since the 1950s.

Problems related to the psychological direction entered linguistics in connection with the ideas of the owners of naturalistic and logical education. In this regard, W. von Humboldt's concept of the speech creative approach to semantic construction deserves attention. in linguistics

The stream of psychologism strongly criticizes naturalism, they believed that the development of language is related to the development of a person's thinking and psyche. Its roots go back to the current of psychologism, which arose on the basis of comparative-historical linguistics in the 19th century.

Professor Geiman Steintal (1823-1899) of the University of Berlin is the main representative of the doctrine of psychologism. He is a student of W. Humboldt and psychologist Johann Herbert. The most important idea in Steintal's teaching is that he considers speech, language as a tool of thinking, a means of expressing thoughts, but psychologism denies that language is a social phenomenon. Psychological concepts express the dependence of language communication on the individual and people, as well as the fact that language is a historical and cultural factor. It should also be noted that the specific features of linguistic biology are expressed in Schleicher's theory, while logic grammarism was revived in Becker's teaching. And Shteytal studies this process in his creative works based on the development of individual behavior and folk psychology. However, psycholinguistics is not developed on the example of one nation [2, B. 83-84].

Psycholinguistics is one of the new fields of linguistics, which is a research in the direction of analyzing issues related to communicative linguistics and text linguistics, an anthropocentric approach to text learning, cognitive linguistics,

pragmalinguistics, linguoculturalism, sociolinguistics, linguistics, ethnolinguistics. closely related to their work.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Linguistics studies not only the psychological character of an individual, but also his speech. For almost a hundred years, in various aspects of psychology, the relationship between the development of speech and the activity of conversation norms in the speech creative approach has been separately studied. Man is known

With a lot of experience, he has the ability to create new sentences using rules. Some general and specific issues of theoretical and practical nature in the field of psycholinguistics are of urgent importance today. First, it is necessary to solve the problem of modeling the semantic structure of the text, adequately reflecting the understanding of the text formed by the interaction between the recipient and the text. Secondly, the semantic structure of the text should be studied in such a way that the results of this research optimize the communication process, machine processing of semantic information, methods of foreign language teaching and pragmatic importance for optimization of translation activities. Psycholinguistic studies within the Russian school of psychology L.S. Vygotsky (1956), A.A. Leontiev (1977, 1981) and A.R. Luria (1959, 1962, 1975, 1979) based on theoretical principles. The psychological school emerged in the first half of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, and studied the functional (task) signs of language, as well as language construction and speech-creative approach to the problem of language and speech. It is known that the task-structural direction is important for psycholinguistics.

Proponents of psycholinguistics focused their attention on the internal side of language, live speech, direct speech process, the meaning of words and sentences, and tried to introduce the concepts and practices of associative psychology. To the study object of psycholinguistics the following are included [1, P. 70]:

1. Mechanism of emergence of speech activity.
2. The formation process of children's speech.
3. Between the speaker and the listener in certain speech situations relationships.
4. Learning and managing the function of information transfer of speech.

Nowadays, this direction of linguistics has expanded, and the issues of human factor in speech, individuality, internal speech and external speech are widely studied.

Psycholinguistic research is primarily focused on the experimental study of text semantics, the formation and structure of text content in the context of semantic perception by its receiver. Following A.A. Leontiev, we read the text as an objectified form of the act of communication (communication situation), parts are the subject of communication, the author and the recipient [6]. The text, in turn: 1) as a derivative (as a form); 2) it is considered as some concept expressed in this form.

The science of psycholinguistics also studies issues such as the problem of the real psychic unity of language, the model of speech formation: speech culture, speech pathology, the interaction between thought and speech, the genesis of speech or the emergence of speech. The name of the Swiss linguist Charles Bally (1865–1974) is well known to linguists of the world. In his teaching, special attention is paid to the issue of studying the state of excited speech. According to the scientist, the occurrence of an affective (exciting) situation in language serves two main purposes:

- 1) expressing the speaker's feelings, mood and evaluating the information being communicated;
- 2) use of certain types of linguistic tools in order to influence the participants of the dialogue [See: 4, P. 60, 68].

In general, Sh.Bally's thoughts on language as a means of influence are noteworthy. Nowadays, these opinions are solved in the discussion of a number of problems activated in such directions as psycholinguistics, communicative linguistics, and pragmalinguistics is important. Sh.Bally, in determining the relationship between intellectual and affective features in the language, is based on the idea that these features are reflected in the human mind in the science of psychology. This duality of thought activity and consciousness translates directly into the language system, and Bally distinguishes between "intellectual" and "affective" language. Emotional-affective language

Bally's ideas about features are important for determining the place of expressiveness in speech activity. The scientist approaches the study of emotional speech activity from a sociological point of view. Such an approach was new for that time, and on this basis a completely new direction in linguistics - linguostylistics -

was born. The productive results of linguostylistics in functional research of the language system and speech activity are known to everyone [4, B. 68]. In semantic-psychological views, the speech process, namely the construction of the speech, the situation of the speech, as well as the issues of the place of the speech in the context, are fully studied and is being studied.

The ideas that exist in linguistics about the essence of the text, its main signs [10, p. 49-70] are also recognized by researchers who have studied the text from the psycholinguistic aspect. In particular, such features as integrity, informativeness, and connectivity of the text that it is the main sign has been noted in the works of a number of psycholinguists [3, B. 8-13; 7, B.10; 8, B. 15]. At the same time, these researchers put forward some views about the psycholinguistic specificity of the text. In particular, Yu.A. Sorokin, who studied the text in a psycholinguistic aspect, approaches its signs of connection and integrity as follows:

"The integrity of the text from a psychological point of view is a hidden projection (conceptual) state that occurs in the process of the interaction between the recipient and the text, as well as the result of the mutual cooperation of parts that are not its construction elements, along with the elements of the communicative language / speech construction [9, B. 61-73]. According to another linguist A.I. Novikov, the integrity of the text is inherent only in its content structure [7, B. 10]. Although this conclusion of A.I. Novikov is correct from a psychological and cognitive point of view, it is controversial because it does not take into account the external structure of the text - the syntactic-structural aspect.

In psycholinguistic research, the study of the text from the point of view of the trinity consisting of "text creator - text - recipient" [5, B. 318] requires an in-depth study of the role of the individual factor in it. It is known that the text is created by a person for a person. This text creation and it indicates that the activity chain consisting of his perception has an anthropocentric character. In psycholinguistic analysis, there are linguistic and non-linguistic factors that operate in the author-receiver relationship, the study of which in harmony allows to obtain the expected results.

The Russian linguist and psychologist V.P. Belyanin, who created many studies on psycholinguistics, created his concept of linguistic and psychological approach to the text in his work entitled "Osnovy psicholingvisticheskoy diagnostiki (modeli mira v literature)".

The scientist's views on the text in the following paragraphs 5-6, taken from this book, deserve special attention in this regard: (5) The text is a system consisting of reality - mind - world view - language - text creator - recipient - text projection. element (V.P. Belyanin noted in this paragraph all linguistic and non-linguistic factors of text creation and perception). (6) The recipient may have their own interpretation of the artwork. This interpretation is with the text it also depends on the psychology of the recipient [3, B. 8-9]. (In this paragraph, V.P. Belyanin emphasized that text perception is a private phenomenon) [2, B. 86-87].

Therefore, it is important for a person to use language and its elements in his socio-political views. In this case, the meanings created with the help of language elements create meaning with the help of language signs, and at the same time, they understand the concepts specific to human behavior.

CONCLUSION

So, naturalism and logicism have a special role in the emergence of linguistic psychologism. Psychology is a form of these processes, and psycholinguistics is the study of other features of language, in particular, the use of language units in the speech process and the individual's explores issues such as expression of meaning and concept related to characteristics, mentality and thinking, character and mood.

Concepts such as language and nation, language and people, language and personality, language and thinking, language and society are inseparable, meaningfully connected, enriching and complementing each other. . People communicate through language. Language is closely related to thinking, it is a tool that materializes and realizes thought. Thinking is the activity of the human higher nervous system and is expressed in language. Its material shell is language. So, without language materials, thought does not emerge. Thought and language form a dialectic unity rich in complex contradictions. It seems that language is understood as the main means of communication of society, so comprehensive study and analysis of language must In addition, determining the criteria of text structure and semantic perception, primarily based on the psycholinguistic analysis of the operative structure of speech activity, the text

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